

**A GEOSPATIAL APPROACH USING GEOMARKETING AND REMOTE
SENSING TO DETERMINE THE BEST LOCATION FOR A NEW MALL IN
NORTHERN RIYADH**

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ABSTRACT

Determining the optimal service location is a fundamental requirement for the success and sustainability of any commercial project. This paper presents a geospatial study that employs remote sensing and Geomarketing techniques to support decision-making related to selecting the best site for a new mall in Northern Riyadh. High-resolution satellite imagery (Spot-6, 1.5 m) acquired at two different dates in 2016 will be analyzed to monitor urban growth, identify residential expansion patterns, and classify building types and construction densities within the micro-geographic zones of the study area. Through assessing population distribution, built-up growth rates, accessibility, and spatial demand indicators, the study aims to estimate the market potential for each district and determine the most suitable location for establishing a major commercial facility. The integration of remote sensing data with Geomarketing principles enables the development of strategic insights for site selection, commercial planning, and future development.

Science plays a vital role in supporting economic development and societal needs across multiple fields—such as agriculture, geology, hydrology, and urban planning—and remote sensing has become one of the most influential tools, offering advanced applications that contribute significantly to business intelligence and spatial decision-making.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Studying Area

2. Riyadh, the capital of Saudi Arabia, is centrally located at the heart of the national transportation network. The city expanded by about 25% between 2005 and 2016, with the northern areas growing more than others due to natural barriers and industrial zones.
3. The study area, covering 240 km² in northern Riyadh, has experienced rapid urban growth and increased human activity. Figure 1.1 shows the city's boundaries in 2005 (yellow) and 2018 (blue), illustrating its horizontal expansion.
4. Riyadh hosts around 30% of the Kingdom's population, and growth is mainly horizontal, as residents prefer standalone buildings for privacy

Figure 1.1 The Growth in Riyadh City Since 2005

Figure 1.2. The Study Area at Northern Riyadh City

4.1. Objective

The objective of this study is as follow:

To improve the best site location methodology by Geomarketing.

4.2. Scope of Study

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the use of high-resolution satellite imagery within the framework of Geomarketing to enhance marketing strategies by integrating spatial information with additional analytic factors. By distinguishing between existing and newly constructed buildings, the study aims to provide decision-makers with more accurate insights that support informed site-selection and strategic planning.

The research will examine how the growth of buildings—and the number of residential units within them—directly influences the market size for the targeted products and services. Since expansion in the built environment contributes to population growth, the study will also assess the characteristics of current and potential residents by analyzing household size and demographic patterns. Using this methodology, population density will be estimated, enabling a more precise understanding of demand distribution across the study area.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2. Best Site Location

The geographic information system can combine spatial data, especially competitor sites, with solutions designed to help open a new facility to enhance the competitiveness of the new entity.

Competitive sites consist of several criteria and are primarily related to consumers and service providers. Here, customer behavior must be considered so that we can meet their demands so that they can have all their requirements in one place (Rafael Suárez, 2012) The opening of a new branch for any company or service is one of the critical works that requires careful study and depends on scientific methodologies in which the review of the situation in various aspects to mitigate any risks that may result from the expansion of activity

The population density that will be used to determine the new location has been studied based on the data obtained from the Statistics Authority (Norat Roig, 2013)

“Qiming” noted that the opening of a new branch for any company is an important decision that should be considered carefully. He described the problem and presented solutions and suggestions to guide users to find the best site. Initially, he suggested a solution without looking at the competitors and then propose another solution, considering the threat resulting from competitor’s activities, he used GIS to designing and study these solutions (Qiming Tian, 2009)

“Xuefeng” Used ArcGIS Geoprocessing to develop spatial analysis modeling and decision making by using implementation technology, modeling and multiple options using ARC GIS, using the classification and reclassification method, and calculating the required spaces to set up the new branch within the conditions and result (Xuefeng, 2010)

“Kazem” presented a study to select the best location for parking as a result of the traffic jam of Tehran city and performed the study of land use and peak areas of traffic and restrictions that prevent the establishment of this position such as cultural restrictions and historical monuments, all those features have been added all to the maps to determine the outputs that correspond with Determine the best location for parking (Kazem, 2015).

CHPATER 3

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

In this section, we will study the data used, the sources of these data, and how it will be processed and used in a manner appropriate to this study, what the variables which used and how can it affect the study, also explain the software that used. What are the satellite data and spatial data, their dates, how can estimate the population by using Remotes sensing, and how we can expect market size for a given product?

3.2. Data Collection

3.2.1. Remote Sensing Data

The primary data used to conduct this study is the Remote sensing data for determining to the urban growth that will require the use of two satellite images in two different dates for the studying area, the specification for it was:

- Satellite: Optical Spot 6
- Resolution: 1.5 m, colour

The first image: its date was January 2016, itis used to create a feature class containing all the existing buildings at that date and classified it according to the building type and construction level.

The second image, figure (3.1): its date was October 2016, itis used to create a feature class containing the new buildings which constructed after the date of the first image in order to know the exact number of new buildings that were created in the study area and which classified according to the building type and construction level, The construction level is:

- a) Basements
- b) Under construction
- c) Construction completed

Here we have the all the building in the studying area, existing and new which classified depend on a field observation (explained in the methodology)

Spot Satellite image for Riyadh city

0 12.5 25 50 75 100
Meters

Figure 3.1. Shown Spot 1.5 m Satellite Image

3.2.3. Open Street Map

The road network in the study area was extracted using the open Street map where the road network in the area was extracted, checked, completed and classified into primary and secondary roads to help classify the buildings where apartments are often built on the main roads, while the villas are inside districts alongside the secondary roads, the roads also help to demarcate the boundaries of the micro-geographic area, the roads also will be taken into consideration for choosing the best location, Figure (3.2).

3.3. Variables

3.3.1. Buildings

Building growth means Growth in market demand for a lot of products like building materials; also the population will live in the new buildings which food, water, and Milk will necessary for them, this variable will have it by Satellite images analysis.

3.3.2. Number of Residential Units Per Residential Buildings Type

This variable changes according to the city and districts, it means the number of units that each residential building type contain, this factor info obtained from the authority of statics.

3.3.3. Family Member

It's a critical variable to estimate the population in the study area which helps to calculate the expected FMCG demand like Milk market size, the family member obtained from the authority of statics.

3.3.4. Vacant Buildings Percentage

According to the authority of statics, there were 12 % of vacant residential units in Riyadh in 2016 which should consider it when calculating the population in the studying area, and this factor affects the expected community so when this factor increase that is mean the population will decrease.

Methodology

The geographical information (GIS) system used in this study in order to identify the existing and new buildings which determined depends on the experience and the images interpretation by manual digitizing. A point placed in front of each building and its classification according to the building type and the construction level, and this done for the images dated at January 2016 and October 2016 .

The types of buildings determined according to the following (the Photographs at the appendices):

- a) The majority of the buildings that are next to the main roads are apartments, which are the features of the building systems in Saudi Arabia, especially in the main cities.
- b) Villas located inside the districts next to secondary roads.
- c) The Esteraha is a building consisting of a few rooms and one floor, it has a small garden with a pool and usually rented during the holidays.
- d) Towers: It is a high building with more than ten floors like hotels that typically located next to some of the main roads such as King Abdul Aziz Road or the Northern Ring.
- e) Mosques: Its shape is distinctive, especially the towards of Mihrab to the Qibla
- f) Gas station.
- g) Malls: which occupy large areas.
- h) Showrooms: usually characterized by the large building and its positions near to the main roads.
- i) Schools and government buildings: characterized by the occupied area and by the method of construction, consisting of four blocks in general and especially for schools.
- j) Palaces and large villas: characterized by the large occupied area which located inside the districts green areas within it.

All types of buildings identified by the satellite image and classified according to the construction level, table (3.2) and the construction level that includes:

- a) Basement
- b) Under construction
- c) Construction is complete

For example, to explain this methodology to determine the market size, we can apply it to calculate the market needs for two kinds of products (FMCG like Milk and building materials like switches and sockets).

In the following will process and study:

- a) Estimating the population in the study area at the Micro-Geographic area levels to using it to estimate the demand for a wide range of services and products.
- b) Estimate the Milk market size and cumulative milk market size at the Micro-Geographic area levels.

- c) Estimate the material of products (switches and sockets) market size and cumulative market size the Micro-Geographic area levels.
- d) Carry out analysis to select the best site location for new services depend on the population density which estimated by using satellite images.

3.4. Used Software

3.4.1. ARC GIS 10.1

ARC GIS (Geographic Information Stem) is a computer-based system that collects, maintains, stores, analyses, outputs and distributes data and spatial information? These systems collect, input, process, analyse, display and produce spatial and descriptive information for specific objectives, and assist planning and decision-making concerning agriculture, urban planning, housing expansion, as well as reading the infrastructure of any city through the creation of called Layers. This system introduces geographic information (maps, aerial photographs, and satellite images), descriptors (names, tables), processing them (revising the error), storing them, retrieving them, analysing them, and analysing them on a computer screen or on paper in the form of maps. , Reports, and graphs.

GIS helps to answer many of the specific questions of specificity (e.g., what is the agricultural pattern, what types of suitable crops to cultivate in the farm unit), measurements, location (What is the relationship between population distribution and Milk or water market size) and hydrological scenarios (what happens if the water used for irrigation).

3.4.2. Erdas Imagine

Erdas Imagine (Earth Resource Development Assessment System) Is a digital image processing software used for analysis and study the satellite imagery, By using it for extraction of Digital Number values of the pixels of the image, and Import export raster's and vectors satellite image, working with various bands of satellite data, to perform

detailed analysis of multiple objects and information using the pattern recognition technique, Land use land cover analysis. Everything you do on Erdas Imagine has a unique concept of Visual Interpretation of satellite imagery.

3.5. Methodology

3.5.1. Workflow

This work started after selecting the studying area which the methodology will be applying to study it, we have to choose the period that we will investigate it then the suitable satellite images which be optical which will be used to extract existing buildings from the older image then determine the growth by extract the new buildings from the latest image, here we should have information about the family member per building unit The following flowchart explains the process.

Figure 3.3 Process Workflow

3.5.2. Satellite Images Analyses

3.5.2.1. January 2016 Satellite Images

The existing construction opportunities in the study area have been extracted to determine the number of existing buildings and classify it according to the building type.

The buildings which under construction were not considered as part of the existing buildings on that date and were therefore considered part of the subsequent buildings.

A description of the existing building included in its attribute table which included the building type and construction level (here the construction stage is considered as completed), Table (3.4) shows the total existing building that detected in January 2016 by Satellite images analysis.

Table 3.4. Total Buildings Scanned in January With its Building Type

Building type	Number of existing buildings	percentage %
villa	44603	88.77
Apartment	3345	6.66
Esteraha	914	1.82
Showroom	526	1.05
Palace	277	0.55
Mosque	237	0.47
School	93	0.19
warehouse	88	0.18
Tower	85	0.17
Gas Station	43	0.09
Governmental	20	0.04
Compound	6	0.01
Industry	3	0.01
Mall	3	0.01
Grand Total	50243	100%

Figure 3.4 Buildings Type Segmentation For January 2016 Buildings.

Table (3.4) and figure (3.4) show that the villas reflect 89% of the existing buildings while the Apartments reflect only 8%

3.5.2.2. October 2016 Satellite Images

The analysis of the following satellite image, dated October 2016, will determine the growth and trends in the study area, with new buildings classified according to building type and construction level (Table 3.5).

Figure 3.5 Buildings Type Segmentation for October 2016 Buildings

Table 3.5. Total Buildings Scanned in October 2016 With its Building Type

Building type	Number of new buildings	percentage %
villa	3626	84.96
Apartment	429	10.05
Showroom	94	2.20
Esteraha	57	1.34
Palace	18	0.42
Mosque	15	0.35
School	9	0.21
Gas Station	8	0.19
Tower	5	0.12
Governmental	3	0.07
warehouse	2	0.05
Compound	1	0.02
Mall	1	0.02
Industry	0	0.00
Grand Total	4268	100%

Also, the majority of the new buildings consist of villas by 85 %, apartments 10 % while the other buildings type include the remains percentage.

3.5.3. Micro-Geographic Segmentation

The study area was divided into Small districts (micro-Geographic area) to identifying the growth at this level to understand the requirements for those areas by determining the business volume and improve the planning. The main roads were selected as the borders for those micro-Geographic areas and labelled with unique numbers starting from 1 to 44, the areas for those districts vary from 2.3 Sq. to 7.7 Sq., only one district its area 23.8 sq. Which contain a large university, districts 25.

Figure 3.6 Micro-Geographic Area Segmentations

3.5.4. Population

Determine the building type and construction level will be valuable for urban area planning and improve business, in other meaning, remote sensing will give us new tool by identifying the population in the districts and micro-geographic area by having information about the total Buildings with its geospatial information, so the buildings will give us the reading and indicator for the population. By using the geospatial data, we will be able to have more accurate information about the community in the studying area and market needs at the districts level. Population information will support decision makers in many sectors (Governmental, business...) to have the right decision depending on the new data.

The total Buildings in January 2016 was 50243 buildings, the residential buildings were 48225 (95.98 % from total), While total new buildings in October 2016 was 4268 buildings, the residential buildings in October were 4037 Buildings (95.43 % from total). According to the 2013 census (Authority of statics) In KSA:

- a) The average units per villa are 3.5 units. (V)
- b) The average units per Apartment are 15.5 units. (A)
- c) The average units per palace are 1 units. (P)
- d) The average population per units is 5.97 person per units. (AVE)
- e) Percentage of non-inhabited buildings in Riyadh is 12 % (88% inhabited). (E).

General Note: depend on 2013 census:

- a- In general, the ground floor in villas is occupied by a Saudi family which have a driver and housekeeper at 50%.

Population in a villa

$$\text{POP VI} = (V * \text{AVE}) + [(\text{driver} + \text{housekeeper}) * 50\%] * E \quad 3.1$$

$$= (3.5 * 5.97) + [(\text{driver} + \text{housekeeper}) * 50\%] * 88\% = 19.26 \text{ person}$$

- b- 38 % of Apartments population is Saudi (25 % of this Saudi segments has a housekeeper)

Population in Apartment

$$\text{POPAPA} = \{(A * \text{AVE}) + [(A * \text{AVE}) * 38\%] * 25\% \} * E \quad 3.2$$

$$= \{(15.5 * 5.97) + [(15.5 * 5.98) * 38\%] * 25\% \} * 88\% = (92.69 + 8.790825) * 88\%$$

$$= 89.16 \text{ person}$$

c- Population in Palace

$$\text{POP PA} = (P * \text{AVE}) + (\text{Driver} + \text{housekeeper} + \text{cooker} + \text{gardener}) * E \quad 3.3$$

$$= (1 * 5.97) + (\text{Driver} + \text{housekeeper} + \text{cooker} + \text{gardener}) * 88\% = (5.98 + 4) * 88\% = 8.77 \text{ person.}$$

Table (3.6) Average Number of Units per Residential Type and Population per Building Type

Building type	Average No. units	Average population per building type
Apartment	15.5	89.16
Villa	3.5	19.26
Palace	1	8.77

After digitizing the existing and new buildings, will give it unique identity by GIS tools, this identity contains: Micro-Geographic code and coordinate system, the other information entered manually during the digitizing like building type and stage.

3.6. Discussion

What we have now, while digitizing the building will have the required information:

- a) Districts code: to know how much building in each districts.
- b) Coordinate system: to create geospatial data
- c) Building type: to Determine the number and type of buildings in each district, if we know the average population in each building type then will determine the population in each district and the study area, here we can expect the milk market size as FMCG study product, or the required products for each building type then expect the potential market size in district and area.

- d) **Building stage:** This information was necessary to determine the required time for each building type to install the products or ready for living. In this study, I hypothesized that they needed time for products installing is the same time that the building will be prepared to live (the time difference will be ignored). This information is useful for the planning team and logistics operation.

3.7. Conclusion

The study area in this section has determined and its general specification and the data which used in this research. Also, The methodology that used to extract and classify the construction, the relationship between the data collected with the buildings were explained to determine Building needs to products or the expected population for each building then at districts levels.

CHAPTER .4

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Introduction

In the following will study how we can use this methodology to determine the population at the districts level and the expected growth, calculate the cumulative number of community in a specific time; also the population estimation will use to develop a methodology to determine the best site location in the study area.

4.2. Cumulative Population

Furthermore, if we want to know the cumulative population for the same periods (three months, six months, one year and two years), namely the expected population growth after three months was 1874 but the cumulative population is the population living in the studying area is the current population (January 2016) plus the expected population growth after three months 1160087 plus 62545 this equal to 1222632 people.

By applying this equation:

$$\text{CUM (n)} = \text{POP (Current)} + \text{Ex POP (n)} \quad 4.1$$

n = after three month, Ex POP (n) = expected population growth after (n) period

POP (current) = January 2016

$$\text{CUM (3)} = 1160087 + 62545 = 1222632 \text{ person}$$

While the six-month population cumulative is three months cumulative plus six months expected growth $1222632 + 12331 = 1234963$ people.

It is essential for forecasting and planning; the decision makers will know with reliability and accuracy what the region needs to, what the market size when the market needs the services, the government will be able to improve its planning to meet the user's requirements.

Table 4.6 Expected Cumulative Population According to the Construction Stage for
Total Buildings

District	January population	October Buildings influences			
		Three Month cumulative	Six Month cumulative	One Year cumulative	Two Year cumulative
1	53017	53619	53638	53805	53805
2	70235	71587	71683	72003	72093
3	61982	63314	63391	63584	63673
4	44802	44918	45014	45281	45281
5	22917	23226	23226	23303	23303
6	18882	19349	19349	19407	19496
7	16030	16415	16473	16935	16953
8	14628	15227	15362	15775	15793
9	22471	22854	22874	23001	23091
10	90508	91166	91224	91798	92065
11	45923	46128	46340	46634	46634
12	56531	57371	57429	57487	57576
13	36723	38028	38356	39105	39194
14	8157	9106	9164	9720	9809
15	68590	72337	72645	73592	73859
16	79836	80701	80797	80925	81014
17	54269	55313	55428	55614	55703
18	8447	9441	9653	10109	10207
19	8900	9476	9515	10148	10148
20	26940	29807	30192	31785	32231
21	41975	43548	43991	44553	44642
22	72172	73336	73471	73734	73734
23	54786	57966	58313	59481	60016
24	8277	10577	11136	11796	12420
25	26431	30534	31246	33082	33528
26	1727	3623	3950	4577	5112
27	8459	12241	13166	15055	15679
28	7158	7351	7659	7717	7717
29	3724	3743	3781	3871	3871
30	8861	9501	9636	10542	10810
31	15456	17152	17287	18781	18959
32	713	732	771	1156	1156
33	790	1118	1349	1888	1888
35	448	544	660	865	865
36	4422	4608	4723	4781	4781
37	35203	36930	37681	38380	38647
38	12056	19376	21130	22692	22871
39	6526	8106	8530	9089	9089
40	13734	18887	19619	21279	21636
41	8590	10465	10773	11725	11903
42	4406	5179	5276	5596	5774
43	10159	12533	13362	14441	15252
44	3771	4746	5247	5999	6088
Total population	1159633	1222178	1234509	1261087	1268363

Figure 4.9 Expected Cumulative Population According to the Construction Stage for Total Buildings

Figure 4.9 analysis: the charts show us that the highest population cumulative was two years later after October 2016 while the lowest population cumulative was three months later after October 2016.

Figure 4.10 The Expected Cumulative Population one Years Later

Figure 4.11 The Expected Cumulative Population Two Years Later

Maps analysis: The figures (4.10 and 4.11) shows the expected cumulative population which calculated for all buildings that detected in January and October 2016, districts with dark blue are the highest population growth while the red colour reflects the lowest.

4.3. Determine The Best Site Location

Many studies carried out to select the best sites for new activities that can provide suitable conditions and meet the specific requirements. The select new location should have criteria, which vary according to the business situation. So far, the population density in these studies has not been given what should have been given to it, but in this research using remote sensing to analyses the high-resolution satellite images to provide us the necessary information that can estimate the population in the studying area (as shown in this study).

The question of choosing the best location for the establishment of facilities and services is a matter that depends on the requirements and needs of the stakeholders and varies

according to the purpose. Selection becomes more complicated depending on the number of conditions required and vice versa. The significant development that is taking place in the Riyadh city especially the study area requires us to develop the methods of study and research commensurate with the massive increase in urban and human activities taking into account the need for new Malls. Several factors can influence selection processes, including the following:

4.3.1. Land Value

The land value determined in many ways, including:

- a) The average value of land sales and purchases in the area, obtained from the Ministry of Justice website.
- b) Distance to the main roads where the land value rises.
- c) Distance to the city centre which the prices in downtown is highest.

Figure (4.33) shows the land price (value) calcification according to the previous three points; the Red colour is the highest price segmentation while the dark blue is the lowest segmentation. The highest segmentation located beside the main two roads (Northern road and King Abdul Al Aziz Road) and between King Abdul Al Aziz Road and King Fahed Road.

Figure 4.33 Land Price Classification

4.3.2. Population Factor

This factor is most important because people who will do the business, purchase and visited retail sites, therefore, a new way of finding out the population density has to be found. So, as we have seen, satellite imagery has helped us detect new and old buildings and calculate the population in areas better than other methods, which depend on tables or another method.

We studied the population in this research and calculated the estimation at districts level to know which places people live? Here the area with high population density will be attractive places for investment and establish new activities. By using ArcGIS the population data converted to population density, Figure (4.34), this will guide the process to target the areas with high population density and give it top priorities. In the figure (4.34) the dark blue reflects the high density which has the number (1) in the legend. Also, the population who lives in the buildings which scanned in January 2016 will be taking into account.

Figure 4.34 Population Density

4.3.3. Land Use

Land use map created by using the Spot 6 satellite image (October 2016) to distinguish the lands to take it in our account and avoid it.

This classification includes, Figure (4.35):

- a) Garden
- b) Mall
- c) Palaces
- d) Unknown area
- e) Industry

Figure 4.35 Land Use.

4.3.4. Distance To The Road Network

There is a wide roads network in the study area, even within the small districts, which is a modern network and is continually being developed, which will help the search and selection of the best location. So as not to put many phenomena on the maps and to avoid set all roads network have placed only the main road network, figure (4.36).

Figure 4.36 Main Roads.

4.3.5. Topographic Factors

The slop in the study area is very low, and the maximum value is 20%. The areas which very slopping is outside the study area. This factor will ignore because it does not affect the selection of sites.

Figure 4.37 The Slop in The Study Area

4.3.6. Climate Factors

Mostly this factor has no significant effect because there is no difference between the temperature in the study area where the temperature in the summer between 40 to 44 degrees.

4.3.7. Competitors (Distance From Current Markets)

When you create an activity that requires careful study of the market. So that the proposed activity should be away from competitors in a way that provides the right investment away from conflicts of interest with them, taking the current competitors and creating a map showing the distance to the competitors must be taken into account which is beneficial for investors.

The choice of the best site based on the required conditions will be more accurate by using remote sensing and Geomarketing, which provides the possibility of dealing with the places through equations given to the computer according to the required factors to offer a number of suggested sites that are compatible to the criteria for the establishment of sites required.

Field survey for the Retail Stores in the study area was conducted to identify the competitors. The search included the branded stores and did not include the hundreds of small stores in the districts, this search was done in two ways:

- a) Field visit
- b) Stores websites

The information that recorded, only retail market name and its location

The following stores recorded in the study area, table (4.18):

While Figure (4.38) show the map of retails location in the study area

Table 4.18 The Retails in The Study Area

Retail brand	number of retails
Aljazeera	1
Al-Sadhan	1
Banda	19
Carrefour	2
Danube	4
Otahaim	7
Tamimi	8
Total Retails	42

Figure 4.38 Retails (Competitors) Location in the Study Area

4.3.8. Land Area

This stage is a complex process, and it depends on dropping the sites of buildings, roads, and land use, by using ArcGIS the results are the lands which has not any activities. Here only the land which has enough area to build the retail building will consider, in Riyadh city the average area for the Malls is 25000 Meter square for that only the land with an area more than 25000 Meter square will talk it into account as in Figure (4.39).

Figure 4.39 Empty Land in The Study Area

4.3.9. Select The Best Location For New Retail

After processing and preparing the required layers, we will be able to start by selecting the suitable sites for that.

We will weight the following layers:

- a) Land price weight is 15 %
- b) Distance to current market 25 %
- c) Population density weight 60 %

We will use raster calculation to calculate the final results as in Figure (4.40). In this map, light blue (number 1) reflect the high priority.

Figure 4.40 Raster Calculation

The results will be a raster, by converting it to layer and by taking the intersection with empty lands as in Figure (4.39), we take into account the flowing at this stage:

- Distance to the main road is less than 100 meters
- Keep only the priority number one and two

The results are the best site location for new retail by considering the previous criteria as in Figure (4.41).

Figure 4.41 Best Site Locations

Conclusion:

It found that the use of remote sensing and GIS provide us with necessary assistance to understand and improve our planning, increase the benefits of using it in industry. The high-resolution satellite images have provided what can be said as a qualitative leap in the search and put the science in the service of the community and the business world.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR FUTURE WORK

5.1. Conclusion

We have developed the mechanism of selecting the best site for the new hypermarket based on the population which estimated as resulting from the analysis of buildings in the study area by using high-resolution satellite images and geographic information systems. There was added a new dimension to the select new place depending on several factors and develop some of those commensurate with the data provided by the Geomarketing tools for more comprehensive to understanding the study area and its components.

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